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ARCHAEOLOGICAL SURVEY IN THE AREA OF RISHAHR (BUSHEHR)

JUNE 1971

We propose to determine archaeologically the location and extent of the Sassanian port city of Rishahr (Rev Ardashir) and its outlying settlements. The study consists of collecting broken pottery from the ground surface and the location by compass bearings of the pottery find spots and archaeological mounding. All photographs are listed in the following sections of the itinerary. The following are the areas which we propose to investigate:

1) Area along the Persian Gulf coast from 1 km. north of the Dastak Fort to 2 km. south.

Photographs: Dastak Fort.

2) Area around Dastak Fort, bordered by Rishahr village, Khasm Khajeh Imamzadeh, Sabzabad and Malek villages, that is up to 1½ km. north, 1 km. east, 2 km. southeast of Dastak Fort.

Photographs: Imamzadeh Shah Nishin.

Tomb stones near Dastak village.

Archaeological mounding between Khasm Khajeh Imamzadeh and Dastak.

Tepe Liyan, Elamite mound.

3) Single site on the road to Hallileh, 4 km. east southeast of the Dastak Fort, exact leveling with instrument and location of site.

Photographs: Mound.

4) If possible, brief investigation of outlying settlements on eroded wadi floor of Bariarroukh River and on Persian Gulf coast from 2 to 5 km. south of Bastak Fort.

Photographs: Close ups of ruined buildings.

Old wells.

The proposed itinerary for the above survey is as follows:

- 1) One day, Thursday afternoon and Friday morning.
- 2) One day, Friday afternoon and Saturday morning.
- 3) Half day, Saturday afternoon.
- 4) One day, Sunday.

رسول اروا

A. G. Williamson

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بوابو بزیدہ یعنی میں یعنی روز جمعہ صبح
 (۳۲۱) ولدہ اور صاحبہ و صاحبہ
 دیکھو درود شریف ۲۳، ۳۰
 برکت بازرگ از صاحب دست
 دقتی از راه برادر بزرگ (مرد)
 لکھنؤ دیکھو بزرگ صاحبان لکھنؤ
 از صاحبہ اسطوری صاحبہ بوقت
 دیکھو دست لکھنؤ بزرگ

(Handwritten signature/initials)

SKETCH PLAN OF AREA OF PROPOSED INVESTIGATION

Scale 1:50,000

